

LEADER-MEMBER EXCHANGE MANIFESTATION, PERFORMANCE, AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE PERSONNEL OF BINAN CITY

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ABSTRACT

A positive leader-member exchange enhanced employee satisfaction, thus leading to increased performance and productivity in the workplace. This study aimed to determine the level of leader-member exchange manifestation, performance, and job satisfaction of the Schools Division Office Personnel of Biñan City. Specifically, the study sought to determine the relationship between leader-member exchange manifestation and job performance and satisfaction. This study employed a descriptive correlational design. The respondents comprised supervisors and personnel of the Schools Division Office of Biñan City, with a total population of 136. When leaders and followers had a good rapport, it boosted morale, increasing output and efficiency on the job. The findings revealed that leader-member exchange manifestation was manifested (3.98). In addition, the findings indicated that the job performance level in terms of task performance (2.82) and contextual performance (3.24) was high, while adaptive performance (2.24) was very high. On the other hand, job satisfaction levels in terms of compensation and benefits (2.78), working environment (3.14), professional growth (3.08), job functions (3.08), and opportunities for promotions (2.98) were satisfied to varying extents. Furthermore, a statistically significant relationship was identified between the leader-member exchange manifestation and job performance, as indicated by probability values below the 0.05 significance threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Likewise, a statistically significant relationship was identified between the leader-member exchange manifestation and job satisfaction, as indicated by probability values below the 0.05 significance threshold, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Based on the results,

an action plan titled Project-BIÑAN was proposed to foster high-quality leader-member relationships, improve job satisfaction, and enhance the overall performance of supervisors and personnel in the Schools Division Office of Biñan.

Keywords: *Leader-Member Exchange, Job Performance, Job Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is a multidimensional concept influencing organizational effectiveness, employee performance, satisfaction, and overall success. When firms face complex issues and diverse workforces, understanding leadership dynamics has never been more important in the present world. On a global scale, firms face various difficulties that highlight the value of competent leadership. One significant concern is the growing diversity of organizations, which includes disparities in culture, background, and job preferences. Leaders in such diverse contexts must understand cultural nuances while cultivating inclusive cultures that value diverse ideas.

As it was, Lartey (2021) mentioned that the connection between Leader–Member Exchange and employee engagement was explored specifically in the context of employees who worked remotely, apart from their supervisors and peers. Based on these results, it was recommended that supervisors maintain a warm and positive relationship with their employees even when they were geographically separated. As illustrated in the Leader-Member Exchange theory, the interaction between a manager and an employee was mutually beneficial and constructive.

The findings of Ghasemy et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of both positive and negative emotional experiences in influencing job satisfaction. However, their findings revealed that only the relationship between positive affect and job satisfaction was significantly mediated by job performance. This suggests that positive emotions enhance performance, which in turn boosts job satisfaction, while no similar mediating effect was found for negative emotions.

Additionally, Herawati et al. (2021) stated that motivation, employee competence, work environment, and employee performance all impacted organizational performance. Employee performance was influenced by their training and growth, motivation, and work environment. Training and development, employee competency, and work environment all impacted organizational performance, which was mediated by employee performance. On the other hand, the performance of employees was not able to counteract the influence that motivation had on the performance of the organization.

Balbuena et al. (2020) concluded that leadership styles influenced organizational performance and satisfaction in the Philippines. Their research demonstrated a robust correlation between the performance of leaders in various higher education institutions in the Philippines and their leadership behaviors. The leadership framework's

complementary functions of task-oriented and people-oriented approaches explained the strong relationship between leader behavior and performance.

As highlighted by Relativo (2024), recent issues in the organizational management of the Department of Education included the pending removal of administrative tasks from teachers. This also posed challenges for non-teaching personnel tasked with performing these duties. Non-teaching staff required additional training or support to effectively manage new responsibilities, particularly if they were unfamiliar with educational policies and procedures. Considering that non-teaching personnel within the Department of Education formed the essential foundation of the educational system and delivered crucial support services enabling teaching staff to fulfill their duties effectively, addressing issues related to Leader-Member Exchange (LMX), job satisfaction, and job performance was imperative.

The study determined the level of leader-member exchange demonstrated by SDO Biñan Personnel and assessed its correlation with job satisfaction and job performance. It provided profound insights for developing individualized interventions and strategies to improve the work dynamics inside the Schools Division Office of Biñan City. The insights stemmed from a thorough and systematic analysis of the essential factors involved, revealing the underlying patterns and relationships among them, offering a comprehensive understanding to guide future decision-making and strategy.

Research Questions

The study's primary objective was to determine the level of Leader-Member Exchange manifestation in SDO Biñan Personnel. It investigated its correlation to job satisfaction and job performance. Specifically, the study sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) manifestation as assessed by supervisors and personnel?
2. Is there a significant difference between the level of leader-member exchange (LMX) manifestation assessed by the Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan?
3. What is the job performance level of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of:
 - 3.1 Task Performance,
 - 3.2 Contextual Performance, and
 - 3.3 Adaptive Performance?
4. What is the job satisfaction level of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of:
 - 4.1 Compensation and Benefits,
 - 4.2 Working Environment,
 - 4.3 Professional Growth,
 - 4.4 Job Functions, and
 - 4.5 Opportunities for Promotion?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of LMX manifestation and the job performance level of SDO Biñan Personnel?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of LMX manifestation and the job satisfaction level of SDO Biñan Personnel?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The study covered a diverse group of respondents comprising supervisors and personnel from the Schools Division Office (SDO) of Biñan. These individuals were chosen as respondents for their valuable administrative and operational dynamics knowledge. With their wide expertise and supervision abilities, supervisors provided crucial insights into implementing policies. Meanwhile, the people who held various administrative and support positions offered a realistic perspective on the SDO's day-to-day issues and efficiency. The respondents gave a thorough insight into SDO Biñan's internal procedures, strengths, and areas for improvement, establishing a solid foundation for the study's suggestions.

The three instruments used in this study were: LMX-7, Job Performance, and Job Performance Satisfaction. These instruments had been validated and used in several studies. LMX-7 is a highly reliable instrument, showing a 0.89 to 0.90 score in Cronbach's alpha, as shown in the studies by Wagner and Koob (2022). Esmane and Quezon (2024) used the Job Performance Questionnaire with a Content Validity Ratio (SVR) of 0.90 and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.899. Solo (2021) developed the Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, which has a Reliability Analysis result of 0.957 in Cronbach's alpha. The same study proved it to be valid and reliable.

A structured data collection method was carried out using adopted questionnaires to explore the manifestation of leader-member interchange, job performance, and job satisfaction among SDO employees. Approval was obtained by a formal request letter to the SDO officials. Following approval, questionnaires were given in both paper and digital modes, with reminders to ensure timely submissions. Data was consolidated, cleansed, processed, and analyzed with the assistance of a statistician. Ethical considerations and confidentiality were strictly enforced throughout the procedure.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Manifestation Level as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor	
	X	VI	X	VI
1. Do you know where you stand with your leader (follower) . . . [and] do you usually know how satisfied your leader (follower) is with what you do?	4.02	M	4.15	M
2. How well does your leader (follower) understand your job problems and needs?	4.11	M	4.05	M
3. How well does your leader (follower) recognize your potential?	4.04	M	3.93	M
4. Regardless of how much formal authority your leader (follower) has built into his or her position, what are the chances that your leader (follower) would use his or her power to help you solve problems in your work?	4.00	M	4.07	M
5. Again, regardless of the amount of formal authority your leader (follower) has, what are the chances that he or she would "bail you out" at his or her expense?	3.61	M	3.61	M
6. I have enough confidence in my leader (follower) that I would defend and justify his or her decision if he or she were not present to do so.	4.12	M	3.90	M
7. How would you characterize your working relationship with your leader (follower)?	4.15	M	3.95	M
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	4.01	M	3.95	M

Legend:

4.20 – 5.00 Highly Manifested 1.80 – 2.59 Almost Not Manifested

3.40 – 4.19 Manifested 1.00 – 1.79 Not Manifested

2.60 – 3.39 Slightly Manifested

Table 1.2 Level of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Manifestation as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel

Indicators	Composite Rank	
	X	VI
1. Do you know where you stand with your leader (follower) . . . [and] do you usually know how satisfied your leader (follower) is with what you do?	4.09	M 1

2. How well does your leader (follower) understand your job problems and needs?	4.08	M	2
3. How well does your leader (follower) recognize your potential?	3.99	M	6
4. Regardless of how much formal authority your leader (follower) has built into his or her position, what are the chances that your leader (follower) would use his or her power to help you solve problems in your work?	4.04	M	4
5. Again, regardless of the amount of formal authority your leader (follower) has, what are the chances that he or she would "bail you out" at his or her expense?	3.61	M	7
6. I have enough confidence in my leader (follower) that I would defend and justify his or her decision if he or she were not present to do so.	4.01	M	5
7. How would you characterize your working relationship with your leader (follower)?	4.05	M	3
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.98	M	

Legend:

4.20 – 5.00 Highly Manifested 1.80 – 2.59 Almost Not Manifested
 3.40 – 4.19 Manifested 1.00 – 1.79 Not Manifested
 2.60 – 3.39 Slightly Manifested

Table 2 Test of Significant Difference on the Assessment of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan on the Level of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) Manifestation

Sub-variables	t value	df	Mean difference	Sig.	Remarks	Decision
Leader-Member Exchange	.476	134	.05517	.122	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	.446					

Level of significance 0.05

Table 3.1 Job Performance Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Task Performance

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. I offer ideas to improve the functioning of the organization.	2.89	HP	3.17	HP	3.03	HP	2
2. I worked weekends or other days off to complete a project or task.	2.55	HP	2.80	HP	2.68	HP	5
3. I volunteered for extra work assignments.	2.57	HP	2.71	HP	2.64	HP	6
4. I came in early or stayed late without pay to complete a project or task.	2.79	HP	2.88	HP	2.84	HP	3
5. I volunteered to attend meetings or work on committees on own time.	2.61	HP	2.78	HP	2.70	HP	4
6. I keep up with developments in the organization	2.93	HP	3.15	HP	3.04	HP	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.72	HP	2.91	HP	2.82	HP	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very High Performance (VHP)
2.50 – 3.24 High Performance (HP)

1.75 – 2.49 Moderate Performance (MP)
1.00 – 1.74 Low Performance (LP)

Table 3.2 Job Performance Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Contextual Performance

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. I maintain emotional balance in difficult situations	2.99	HP	3.29	VHP	3.14	HP	7
2. I helped new employees get oriented to the job.	3.12	HP	3.39	VHP	3.26	VHP	4
3. I accept good ideas from my co-workers.	3.28	VHP	3.37	VHP	3.33	VHP	2.5
4. I socialize with my co-workers during my free time.	3.15	HP	3.27	VHP	3.21	HP	5
5. I am willing to help my co-workers if needed.	3.44	VHP	3.34	VHP	3.39	VHP	1
6. I avoid criticism and back fighting of co-workers in my workplace.	3.08	HP	3.15	HP	3.12	HP	8

7. I can handle disagreements with the people inside the organization.	3.12	HP	3.22	HP	3.17	HP	6
8. I maintain good relationships with my co-worker.	3.33	VHP	3.32	VHP	3.33	VHP	2.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.19	HP	3.29	VHP	3.24	HP	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very High Performance (VHP) 1.75 – 2.49 Moderate Performance (MP)
2.50 – 3.24 High Performance (HP) 1.00 – 1.74 Low Performance (LP)

Table 3.3 Job Performance Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Adaptive Performance

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. I easily adapt to physical demands or changes at work	3.17	HP	3.34	VHP	3.26	VHP	6
2. I seek colleagues' or supervisors' support when overwhelmed.	3.16	HP	3.29	VHP	3.23	HP	7
3. I'm open to new ideas when solving complex problems.	3.31	VHP	3.41	VHP	3.36	VHP	3
4. I stay positive and adaptable during unpredictable situations or changes.	3.29	VHP	3.39	VHP	3.34	VHP	5
5. I seek learning opportunities to enhance my skills and knowledge.	3.29	VHP	3.41	VHP	3.35	VHP	4
6. I maintain professionalism and respect in all interactions.	3.37	VHP	3.46	VHP	3.42	VHP	1.5
7. I respect cultural differences, fostering an inclusive environment.	3.32	VHP	3.51	VHP	3.42	VHP	1.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.27	VHP	3.40	VHP	3.34	VHP	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very High Performance (VHP) 1.75 – 2.49 Moderate Performance (MP)
2.50 – 3.24 High Performance (HP) 1.00 – 1.74 Low Performance (LP)

Table 4.1 Job Satisfaction Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Compensation and Benefits

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. The organization has an appropriate salary scale or pay structure based on the educational qualification and related work experience of the employees.	2.74	S	2.95	S	2.85	S	4.5
2. Adequacy of the salary to support living expenses.	2.55	S	2.85	S	2.70	S	7
3. Personal growth and financially stable in this organization.	2.72	S	2.98	S	2.85	S	4.5
4. Implementation of regular payment and fair wages.	2.78	S	2.93	S	2.86	S	3
5. A prompt payment for the overtime pay for services rendered is given.	2.53	S	2.76	S	2.65	S	8
6. Benefits from SSS, PAG-BIG, & PhilHealth suffice the future needs of the family in case of emergencies.	2.73	S	3.05	S	2.89	S	1
7. Provisions for salary increase every year based with the performance of the employees.	2.75	S	2.93	S	2.84	S	6
8. Modes of incentives given to employees with considerable amount.	2.83	S	2.90	S	2.87	S	2
9. Provisions for educational benefits are given among employees.	2.57	S	2.71	S	2.64	S	9.5
10. Provisions for giving cash awards to outstanding employees every year.	2.57	S	2.71	S	2.64	S	9.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.67	S	2.88	S	2.78	S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 – 2.49 Less Satisfied (LS)

2.50 – 3.24 Satisfied (S)

1.00 – 1.74 Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 4.2 Job Satisfaction Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Working Environment

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. Personal growth by learning various skills in my work.	3.04	S	3.24	S	3.14	S	7

2. A positive image of the organization towards my friends and family.	3.19	S	3.22	S	3.21	S	2.5
3. The culture of the organization has encouraged its employees in viewing themselves as part of the team.	3.15	S	3.27	VS	3.21	S	2.5
4. Availability of mechanisms to resolve conflicts in the organization.	2.86	S	3.02	S	2.94	S	10
5. Employees work hand in hand to meet and achieve organizational goals and objectives.	3.00	S	3.17	S	3.09	S	9
6. An atmosphere of interdependence between supervisor and employees.	3.11	S	3.24	S	3.18	S	4
7. Distance supervision for the responsible employees.	3.07	S	3.17	S	3.12	S	8
8. Demonstration of respect and positive attitude towards work of other employees.	3.17	S	3.29	VS	3.23	S	1
9. A highly conducive and satisfactory community and academic environments for job satisfaction.	3.08	S	3.22	S	3.15	S	5.5
10. Enforcing appropriate working hours for employees.	3.07	S	3.22	S	3.15	S	5.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.07	S	3.21	S	3.14	S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 – 2.49 Less Satisfied (LS)

2.50 – 3.24 Satisfied (S)

1.00 – 1.74 Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 4.3 Job Satisfaction Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Professional Growth

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. Sufficient funds and resources are given among employees to take advantage of participating in professional development activities such as training, conferences, and the like.	3.12	S	3.20	S	3.16	S	1.5
2. The management provides the employees with opportunities to grow and develop their potentials and skills.	3.11	S	3.20	S	3.16	S	1.5
3. Teamwork approach emphasized in the organization for better work relations.	3.06	S	3.24	S	3.15	S	3.5
4. Provision of other opportunities to grow and develop potentials and skills.	3.05	S	3.17	S	3.11	S	6.5

5. The avenue to be promoted in a higher position is being worked out by the management for the employees.	2.67	S	3.07	S	2.87	S	10
6. Leadership is promoted and nurtured among employees.	3.01	S	3.20	S	3.11	S	6.5
7. This organization provides the employees an equal opportunity to attend various trainings related to their work.	3.06	S	3.24	S	3.15	S	3.5
8. An open opportunity to acquire and make use of new knowledge, skills, and training along the thrust of instruction, community extension, and research.	3.11	S	3.15	S	3.13	S	5
9. The organization ensures a clear career path for the employees.	2.68	S	3.10	S	2.89	S	9
10. Employees take hold whatever chances of promotion the organization has proposed.	2.88	S	3.12	S	3.00	S	8
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.98	S	3.17	S	3.08	S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 – 2.49 Less Satisfied (LS)

2.50 – 3.24 Satisfied (S)

1.00 – 1.74 Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 4.4 Job Satisfaction Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Job Functions

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. The set of responsibilities stipulated in the job description.	2.75	S	3.12	S	2.94	S	10
2. Job brings positive changes to me.	3.01	S	3.27	VS	3.14	S	4
3. Recognition by the management or heads of department on the good work I accomplished.	2.86	S	3.15	S	3.01	S	8
4. The sense of teamwork applied in the organization, thus, keeping the employees' relationship strong and healthy.	2.96	S	3.24	S	3.10	S	6
5. The degree of independence associated in my work roles and functions keeping it more challenging and fulfilling.	3.00	S	3.34	VS	3.17	S	2.5

6. Contentment on the job functions given, that employees active and satisfied in doing the workloads set.	2.86	S	3.17	S	3.02	S	7
7. Valuing organizational change such as job rotation, change of office, etc.	2.77	S	3.17	S	2.97	S	9
8. The sense of belongingness and camaraderie I feel in the organization especially when accomplishing tasks.	3.01	S	3.22	S	3.12	S	5
9. I utilize whatever available tools and resources to do my job well.	3.06	S	3.27	VS	3.17	S	2.5
10. The kind of work I do in the organization.	3.06	S	3.29	VS	3.18	S	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.93	S	3.22	S	3.08	S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 – 2.49 Less Satisfied (LS)

2.50 – 3.24 Satisfied (S)

1.00 – 1.74 Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 4.5 Job Satisfaction Level of Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Opportunities for Promotions

Indicators	Personnel		Supervisor		Composite		Rank
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI	
1. A standard procedure in the promotion and strict adherence to criteria set in ranking.	2.83	S	3.76	VS	3.30	VS	1
2. Basis of performance assessment for promotion.	2.72	S	3.02	S	2.87	S	10
3. I clearly understand the practice of promotion in the organization specifically when it comes to the educational attainment and training attended.	2.91	S	3.07	S	2.99	S	3
4. I am happy with the current status of my employment in the organization.	2.79	S	3.12	S	2.96	S	6
5. The opportunity given by the organization to the employees' career advancement is impartial.	2.74	S	3.02	S	2.88	S	9
6. The promotional policy in the organization is aligned based on the institutional, statutory and regulatory requirements and qualification of the employees.	2.86	S	3.07	S	2.97	S	4

7. Fairness in the implementation of promotion policies in the school is observed.	2.91	S	3.00	S	2.96	S	6
8. Consideration of factors as performance ratings, education and training experience, outstanding accomplishments, personality traits and leadership potentials in the promotion process.	2.98	S	3.10	S	3.04	S	2
9. Chances to fill up higher position from within the organization whenever possible.	2.76	S	3.07	S	2.92	S	8
10. Information to advertise opportunities for promotion for interested employees to apply.	2.85	S	3.07	S	2.96	S	6
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.83	S	3.13	S	2.98	S	

Legend:

3.25 – 4.00 Very Satisfied (VS)

1.75 – 2.49 Less Satisfied (LS)

2.50 – 3.24 Satisfied (S)

1.00 – 1.74 Not Satisfied (NS)

Table 5 Test of Significant Relationship between Level of LMX Manifestation and Job Performance Level of SDO Biñan Personnel

Level of LMX Manifestation	Job Performance Level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
LMX Manifestation	Task Performance	.493**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Contextual Performance	.565**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Adaptive Performance	.924**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 6 Test of Significant Relationship between Level of LMX Manifestation and Job Satisfaction Level of SDO Biñan Personnel

Level of LMX Manifestation	Job Satisfaction Level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Client Appraisal	Compensation and Benefits	.383**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Working Environment	.763**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Professional Growth	.632**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

Job Functions	.781**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀
Opportunities for Promotions	.749**	.000	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

Table 7 Proposed Action Plan

KRA		OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	TIMEFRAME	PERSONNEL INVOLVED	KPIS
LEADER-MEMBER EXCHANGE		Communication	Conduct LMX Training Sessions for SDO Biñan Personnel	Q2 - 2025	Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan	85% of personnel achieving set KPIs
		Relationship	Implement Regular One-on-One Check-ins	Weekly	Supervisors	
		Transparency	Launch a Feedback System (Upward & Downward)	Q2 to Q3 - 2025	HR Department	90% compliance in one-on-one check-ins and coaching sessions
JOB PERFORMANCE	TASK PERFORMANCE	Set Clear Task Expectations	Define and communicate clear task expectations.	1 month	Management	100% of job descriptions updated
			Provide detailed job descriptions.			90% of employees are aware of task expectations

	Provide Necessary Resources	Ensure employees have the tools and resources needed.	Ongoing	HR & Department Heads	100% of resource needs met
		Regularly review resource needs.			85% positive feedback on resources
	Offer Task-Specific Training	Identify training needs for specific tasks.	3 months	HR & Department Heads	70% of employees are completing training
		Provide relevant training programs.			20% improvement in task performance
	Implement Regular Check-Ins	Schedule regular check-ins to monitor task progress.	Ongoing	Management	100% of employees receive regular check-ins
		Provide feedback and support.			80% of tasks completed on time
	Encourage Collaboration	Promote teamwork and collaboration on tasks.	6 months	HR & Management	50% of tasks completed collaboratively
		Facilitate team-building activities.			85% positive feedback on teamwork

KRA		OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	TIMEFRAME	PERSONNEL INVOLVED	KPIS
JOB CATEGORY	COMPENSATION	Improve Benefits Package	Survey employees to identify desired benefits.	4 months	HR Department	80% of the new benefits introduced

JOB SATISFACTION	OPPORTUNITIES FOR PROMOTIONS		Introduce new benefits (e.g., health, wellness programs).			Employee retention rate \geq 85%
		Enhance Work-Life Balance	Introduce flexible working hours.	6 months	HR & Management	60% of employees use flexible work options
			Implement remote work policies.			Work-life balance satisfaction score \geq 75%
		Establish Clear Promotion Criteria	Develop transparent criteria for promotions.	2 months	HR & Management	100% of the promotion criteria documented
	Communicate the criteria to all employees.		90% of employees are aware of the criteria			
	Create Career Development Plans	Work with employees to create individual career development plans.	3 months	Management	100% of employees with career development plans	
		Review and update plans regularly.			80% of plans are reviewed annually	
	Promote Internal Hiring	Prioritize internal candidates for open positions.	Ongoing	HR & Management	50% of open positions filled internally	
		Communicate internal job openings effectively.			Employee satisfaction score \geq 80%	

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: *What is the level of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) manifestation as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel?*

Table 1.1

The level of leader-member exchange (LMX) as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel, shown in Table 1.1, indicated that Leader-Member Exchange was Manifested. Moreover, the highest rated indicator for supervisors and personnel was 4.15, which implied that supervisors know where they stand along with their subordinates. On the other hand, personnel have a good working relationship with their leader. However, the lowest rated indicator for both was 3.61; these implied that supervisors and personnel have the same perception of formal authority.

It implies effective communication where expectations and feedback are openly shared, allowing both parties to understand each other's satisfaction. This transparency fosters trust, respect, and psychological safety, contributing to a positive work environment. It also suggests a culture of openness and accountability that encourages honest dialogue and continuous growth, highlighting strong relationships and effective leadership or followership within the organization.

The findings of Erschens et al. (2024) highlighted the necessity for stress prevention programs involving leader-members. They showed how the perceived value of social ties at work significantly contributed to job stress among healthcare professionals. These results underscore the importance of fostering supportive workplace relationships as a key strategy in mitigating stress and promoting overall well-being in high-pressure environments.

Lopez-Zapata et al. (2024) demonstrated that the association between transformational leadership and task performance was mediated by social exchange factors, such as perceived organizational support and leader-member exchange (LMX). However, there was no statistically significant mediating effect of work involvement.

Moreover, Wang et al. (2024) showed that empathetic leaders boosted employee creativity by understanding their emotions, which helped improve productivity and achieve business goals. Empathy also strengthened leader-employee relationships, enhancing communication, fairness, and motivation to share ideas. Overall, leadership empathy was beneficial and worth developing in the workplace.

Table 1.2

The level of leader-member exchange (LMX) as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel, shown in Table 1.2, indicated that Leader-Member Exchange was Manifested. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 4.09, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel are satisfied with their interaction with one another. However, the lowest indicator 3.61

suggested that there is a small chance that they will bail out one another in their own expense.

The level of leader-member exchange (LMX) manifestation, as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel, is anchored with a strong connection between one another. The level of trust and respect between the leader and member can determine relationship strength. Additionally, this implies that high-quality relationships thrive positively, however, low-quality relationships may result in poor leader-member exchange manifestation. This could be attributed to shared values, goals, reciprocity, or organizational culture. It can be concluded that Leader-Member Exchange among SDO Biñan Personnel is significant, as indicated by the overall assessment of 3.98. The highest computed mean score implied that SDO Biñan Personnel are satisfied with their relationship with their leader or follower. Leader and member characteristics influence LMX relationships and develop through role-making.

Sa'adah, N., & Rijanti, T. (2022) stated that Leader-Member Exchange improves health professionals' performance. Thus, higher Leader-Member Exchange boosts performance. So, strengthening the Leader-Member Exchange will boost performance.

Conversely, Assefa et al. (2024) highlighted that the intensity of a leader's relationship with a subordinate impacts the subordinate's view of organizational fairness, thus affecting the subordinate's inclination to voice concerns regarding the institution's issues or areas for enhancement.

Additionally, Yu et al. (2024) highlighted that the LMX theory continues to be a significant leadership theory that investigates the significance of leader-member interactions and the impact that these interactions have on work results.

Research Question 2: *Is there a significant difference between the Level of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) manifestation as assessed by the supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan?*

There was no significant difference in the assessment of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan on the Level of leader-member exchange (LMX) manifestation. It generated computed probability values of .122, which was greater than the significance level of 0.05 using T-test; thus, the null hypothesis was accepted.

In their relationship, it implies they have a mutual understanding and alignment. This same perception suggests that both parties view their contacts in a comparable manner, which may have resulted in a great deal of positive outcomes.

In accordance with Sobral et al. (2024), leaders can develop one-of-a-kind ties with their followers, which ultimately results in diverse relationship characteristics among members of the same team. These relationships are developed via the social interactions between leaders and followers; trust and support are characteristics reflective of high-quality interactions that cultivate loyalty and respect for one another. These

relationships are formed through the establishment of these relationships. The leadership literature has been altered due to the LMX theory, which has called into question two commonly held assumptions. The first of these beliefs is that leaders have a consistent leadership style with every follower, and the second is that followers in a workgroup are all the same.

In addition, Vriend et al. (2020) highlighted that high-quality LMX contacts encourage unethical intentions toward leaders to satisfy positive reciprocity motives. In contrast, low-quality LMX relationships encourage unethical intentions toward oneself to resolve negative reciprocity reasons. This is an additional point of interest that has been brought to light. In light of this, it is abundantly clear that while analyzing the effects of LMX, it is vital to consider both positive and negative appreciation motives. This is because LMX has both positive and negative consequences.

Lastly, Caputo et al. (2025) indicated that LMX served as a resource when it was more powerful, reducing the impact of abusive supervision on job satisfaction. Registered nurses who reported higher levels of job satisfaction and a higher level of LMX consensus were more likely to have plans to switch wards than nurses who worked in groups with lower levels of LMX consensus.

Research Question 3: *What is the job performance level of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Task Performance, Contextual Performance, and Adaptive Performance?*

The job performance level, as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel in terms of Task Performance, shown in Table 3.1, indicated that Job Performance was High. Moreover, the highest-rated indicator, 3.04, implied that the Supervisors and Personnel keep up with developments. However, the lowest indicator, 2.64, suggested they don't prioritize extra work assignments.

Table 3.1

This suggests that task performance is significant among the Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan. According to the indicators, supervisors and personnel prioritize organizational advancement. This indicates that the contributions of both supervisors and personnel can enhance the organization's overall functions. It can be concluded that the task performance among the Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan has high performance with a general assessment of 2.82. The highest calculated mean score indicates that most supervisors and personnel prioritize organizational development. Organizational development enhances engagement, productivity, and flexibility, improving communication, teamwork, and overall performance. The lowest computed mean score indicates that supervisors and personnel are reluctant to volunteer for additional work assignments, potentially leading to increased strain and stress among current staff, which may negatively impact morale and productivity, and hinder the completion of tasks and projects.

Kamal et al. (2024) indicated that advocating for change within organizations benefits individuals and organizations. The research demonstrates that implementing a transparency framework concerning organizational decisions and the change process can enhance organizational change initiatives.

In relation to this, the findings of Xia et al. (2024) demonstrated a significant favorable influence of the leader's ethical voice on the task performance of subordinates. Furthermore, it was revealed that identifying subordinates with the leader and the interchange between leader and member served as mediators in the relationship, both independently and in conjunction as a sequence of mediating factors. Turk et al. (2022) found that volunteering improves health and well-being, especially when tailored to link workers with clients. Social prescribing may require additional support for volunteers.

As assessed by Supervisors and Personnel in terms of Contextual Performance, shown in Table 3.2, the job performance level was High. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 3.39, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel are willing to help when needed. However, the lowest indicator, 3.12, suggested that they avoid conflicts in the workplace.

Table 3.2

This suggests that, in general, supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan are willing to help their co-workers if needed. The results indicate a varied contextual job performance perspective for SDO Biñan Personnel. Assisting colleagues cultivates a constructive and efficient workplace by enhancing relationships, elevating morale, promoting collaboration, and potentially resulting in greater job satisfaction, performance, and retention. On the other hand, supporting colleagues can create a fantastic work environment, but going above and beyond can lead to burnout, mental tiredness, and slow productivity and growth.

It can be concluded that the contextual performance of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan has high performance, as indicated by the overall assessment of 3.24. The highest mean score implies that most supervisors and personnel are willing to help their co-workers. This demonstrates that a culture of support and collaboration can create a more positive and cohesive workplace environment. Despite having the lowest mean score, supervisors and personnel perform well in avoiding workplace criticism and backbiting of co-workers.

Studies conducted by Tenakwah et al. (2024) emphasized the importance for managers to evaluate the role of support from colleagues and supervisors critically. This suggests that organizations ought to emphasize the importance of adequate training for managers and supervisors to enhance their ability to provide social support to employees. Organizations have the potential to develop a workplace culture that is both healthy and supportive, which can lead to improvements in employee engagement, motivation, and performance.

Furthermore, Susilastuti (2024) demonstrated that self-efficacy significantly and positively influences health workers' emotional well-being and performance. In addition, the support from colleagues has positively and significantly impacted the mental well-being of health workers and their professional performance.

Table 3.3

As assessed by supervisors and personnel in terms of Adaptive Performance, shown in Table 3.3, the job performance level was Very High. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 3.42, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel maintain professionalism and an inclusive environment. However, the lowest indicator, 3.23, suggested they seek support when overwhelmed.

This suggests that Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan uphold professionalism and demonstrate respect for cultural differences while prioritizing cultural inclusivity within the workplace. Fostering a healthy and productive work environment is crucial for maintaining professionalism. This encompasses consistently demonstrating elevated standards of conduct, including respect, integrity, reliability, and proficient communication. An inclusive workplace recognizes and values the importance of culturally diverse perspectives, experiences, and abilities. It can be concluded that the adaptive performance of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan is very high, as indicated by the overall assessment of 3.34. The highest mean score implies that most supervisors and personnel know professionalism and maintain inclusivity in the workplace. However, the lowest mean score suggests that despite workplace inclusivity, there are still hesitations in seeking help when overwhelmed at work.

Moreover, Ja'is, M., Suyono, J., & Elisabeth, D. R. (2024) emphasized that professionalism modifies employee performance. Professionalism boosts employee performance. However, a lack of professionalism will lower quality, hurting employee performance.

Likewise, Dhal et al. (2025) further noted that culturally competent professionals can better handle cross-cultural difficulties and help varied team members feel valued and respected. Making the team inviting and encouraging everyone to contribute can improve team chemistry, reduce conflict, and boost performance.

Steeh et al. (2025) also emphasized agile goal-making procedures and showed how agile approaches gave teams liberty in developing, revising, and prioritizing goals.

Research Question 4: *What is the job satisfaction level of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan in terms of Compensation and Benefits, Working Environment, Professional Growth, Job Functions, and Opportunities for Promotions?*

Table 4.1

As assessed by supervisors and personnel in terms of Compensation and Benefits, shown in Table 4.1, the job satisfaction level was Satisfied. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 2.89, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel believed that benefits would suffice future needs. However, the lowest indicator, 2.64, suggested that they seek provisions for education and cash incentives.

This suggests that SDO Biñan supervisors and staff believe GSIS, PAG-IBIG, and PhilHealth benefits cover family emergency needs. People can always get government help in emergencies. It can be concluded that the compensation and benefits of supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan were satisfactory, as indicated by the overall assessment of 2.78. The highest mean score implies that benefits would suffice for future needs. However, the lowest mean score implies that despite all the benefits, they still seek provisions for other benefits, such as educational benefits and other performance-based incentives.

According to Cui (2024), specific components of employee benefit programs, including health insurance, training and development opportunities, and work-life balance policies, substantially influence the job satisfaction of sales professionals.

In contrast, Akinyemi et al. (2022) emphasized that compensation is frequently seen as a hygiene element in motivational theories, indicating that while reductions in income may lead to unhappiness, increases in compensation do not necessarily enhance pleasure.

However, Kashive et al. (2025) stated that flexible work policies highlighted a dimension in non-monetary benefits, which they transformed into an influential determinant in elevating women's job satisfaction. It was considered that these elements significantly influenced one's working experience, leading to the conclusion that policies were essential for fostering gender equity in the workplace. These flexible working policies gave women control and flexibility in choosing personal and professional balance.

Table 4.2

As assessed by supervisors and personnel in terms of Working Environment, shown in Table 4.2, the job satisfaction level was Satisfied. Moreover, the highest rated indicator 3.23 implied that that the Supervisor and Personnel demonstrate respect and positive attitude to each other. However, the lowest indicator, 2.94, suggested that there's a lack of mechanisms in resolving conflict.

This suggests that most SDO Biñan Personnel demonstrate respect and a positive attitude towards the work of other employees. This serves as a reflection on how their families and friends see the organization. However, there is little focus on the availability of mechanisms to resolve organizational conflicts that may affect their working environment. It can be concluded that the working environment among the supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan is satisfactory, with a general assessment of 3.14. The highest computed mean score implies that SDO Biñan Personnel highly regard respecting other employees. Conversely, the lowest calculated means suggests that while there is respect, there is a need to improve the mechanisms in resolving conflicts. In the absence of these channels, the organization may face a build-up of concerns, negatively affecting the workplace.

Drawing upon these findings, Mwogereze (2023) stated that employees must demonstrate respect and maturity towards one another. A successful organization requires a collaborative effort from both employees and employers.

In addition, Andriani et al. (2023) highlighted that the quality of work and production levels of employees are significantly influenced by the organizational environment for individuals, which is thus a primary consideration for the company. It showed a strong link between the working environment and hotel employees' happiness with their jobs.

On the other hand, the low mean score coincides with Liam (2024), who emphasized that effective conflict management requires education and training to provide individuals and organizations with the essential skills and techniques. The purpose of these strategies is to inspire collaborative problem-solving through theoretical understanding and practical application, as well as to improve communication and promote constructive debate.

Table 4.3

As assessed by supervisors and personnel in terms of Professional Growth, shown in Table 4.3, the job satisfaction level was Satisfied. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 3.16, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel believe there are enough resources and enough growth opportunities. However, the lowest indicator, 2.87, suggested that the management is creating a path for people to advance.

This suggests that professional growth is significant among SDO Biñan Personnel. Based on the indicators, it can be observed that the organization actively facilitates opportunities for professional advancement among its employees. Employees are provided adequate financial resources and support for enhancing their skills through various training programs and similar initiatives. It can be concluded that professional growth among the supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan is satisfactory, with a general assessment of 3.08. The highest means implies that a significant majority of the personnel at SDO Biñan receive opportunities for professional development, facilitated by the financial resources and support provided by the organization. The lowest means, on the other hand, suggests that there may be some individuals who are uncertain as to whether

or not the management is currently constructing or preparing a method or pathway for employees to be promoted to higher positions within the firm.

Based on the findings of Jogi et al. (2023), work satisfaction is a prominent factor that plays a big role in contributing to employees' decisions regarding whether or not they intend to remain with a business or leave it. In doing so, they highlight the idea that job satisfaction is comprised of a number of variables, each of which has the potential to affect turnover intention in both positive and negative ways.

Lim (2024) brought attention to the intricate relationship between job happiness, the prevalence of different leadership styles, and the efficiency of a company. Within the context of boosting job satisfaction and employee performance, she emphasized the critical significance of transformative leadership in conjunction with a supportive work environment.

Additionally, Saharso et al. (2024) carried out a study to determine the extent to which the resources that are accessible in the workplace and the ambiance of the workplace have an impact on the level of job satisfaction that physicians experience. The availability of work resources has been found to have a positive link with increasing levels of job satisfaction, according to the findings of a recent study.

As an additional point of interest, Cox (2025) underlined the significance of worker happiness as a key component in building resilient organizations. He said that this was extremely important. Her presentation showed the audience that a high level of job satisfaction was the relationship between greater staff retention, higher engagement, and enhanced customer experiences. She also brought this idea to the attention of the audience.

Lastly, when it comes to attracting and maintaining talent, Lesonsky (2025) performed a study to assess the significance of employee happiness and job satisfaction. This research was undertaken in order to determine the significance of these factors. During the investigation, she concluded that companies that placed a greater emphasis on the contentment of their workers were better equipped to deal with changes in the workplace and to retain their most talented personnel.

Table 4.4

The job satisfaction level, as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel in terms of Job Functions, shown in Table 4.4, was Satisfied. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 3.18, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel are satisfied with their work. However, the lowest indicator, 2.94, suggested that duties and responsibilities may affect satisfaction.

This suggests that job functions are significant among SDO Biñan Personnel. Based on the indicators, the leaders and employees are content with the nature of their work inside the organization. However, the responsibilities specified in the job description

are not given much attention. It can be concluded that job functions among the supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan are satisfactory, with a general assessment of 3.08. The highest computed mean score implies that most SDO Biñan Personnel have a high regard for their work in the organization. Conversely, the lowest computed mean score suggests that while employees are satisfied with their work, there is low regard for the responsibilities stipulated in their job description.

Relative to this, Petrilli et al. (2024) emphasized that organizations can adopt actionable strategies to promote positive leader–member exchanges and improve employees' adjustment to different work modes to protect them from exhaustion and dissatisfaction and boost their motivation to stay, such as involving employees in dialogue on the best work mode for their tasks and organizational goals; establishing regular systems to monitor employees' needs and levels of adjustment.

In addition, Ji et al. (2022) stated that LMX may directly predict work-related flow and indirectly anticipate it through job crafting by augmenting structural job resources and challenging job demands, thereby offering novel insights for improving the flow experiences of medical professionals.

However, Indeed Editorial Team (2025) emphasized that one problem with this idea is that it assumes every team member is the same, which isn't always the case. Different employees have different skills and levels of reliability, so it's up to the boss to give the right jobs to the right people.

Table 4.5

As assessed by Supervisors and Personnel in terms of Opportunities for Promotions, shown in Table 4.5, the job satisfaction level was Satisfied. Moreover, the highest rated indicator, 3.30, implied that the Supervisor and Personnel are satisfied with the set of guidelines for promotion. However, the lowest indicator, 2.87, suggested that there might be a factor about the basis of assessment for promotion.

This suggests that opportunities for promotions are significant among SDO Biñan Personnel. Based on the indicators, when it comes to the promotion process, the employees are pleased with the regular approach and their tight adherence to the criteria established for rating.

It can be concluded that job opportunities for promotions among the supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan are satisfactory, with a general assessment of 2.98. The highest computed mean score implies that they trust the set of procedures and guidelines in promoting employees. However, the lowest computed mean score implies that despite an effective promotion process, there might be factors affecting the basis of performance for promotion.

According to Madugu et al. (2023), an effective promotion policy and its implementation would boost employee morale in meeting commitments, resulting in job

satisfaction. It suggests that job satisfaction and promotion impact great performance by boosting staff morale and reducing labor turnover.

Nasar et al. (2024) found that matching job roles with employees' skills and talents boosts job satisfaction. Effective promotion systems enhance employee performance. Overall, aligning job characteristics with employee abilities improves organizational performance.

Research Question 5: *Is there a significant relationship between the level of LMX manifestation and the job performance level of SDO Biñan Personnel?*

Table 5

There was a significant relationship between the LMX manifestation and job performance level. It generated r values ranging from .493 to .924, which were interpreted as low positive to very high positive correlation, correlating LMX Manifestation and Job Performance. The computed probability values of .000 were less than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

It can be concluded that LMX Manifestation is significantly related to the Job Performance Level of SDO Biñan Personnel. This implies that the higher the LMX Manifestation, the higher the Job Performance.

In corroboration of such findings, Willie (2025) underscored that job performance is greatly improved by high-quality LMX relationships that are marked by trust, mutual respect, and open communication. In addition to bolstering Organizational Citizenship Behaviors, these connections increase work satisfaction, team engagement, and productivity.

Furthermore, Ogunja et al. (2025) highlighted the positive correlations between Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) and employee well-being, job satisfaction, and organizational resilience, implying that LMX fosters a unified and robust work environment that improves team efficacy and long-term development. These findings identified LMX as a strategic tool for increasing employee engagement and competitive organizational performance.

Additionally, Wagner et al. (2022) found that social workers with good LMX relationships have more job resources, enjoy teamwork, and had more control over their work. A positive team atmosphere increases work engagement and mediates the link between LMX and engagement. However, good LMX relationships alone did not directly boost work engagement.

Research Question 6: *Is there a significant relationship between the level of LMX manifestation and the job satisfaction level of SDO Biñan Personnel?*

Table 6

There was a significant relationship between the LMX manifestation level and job satisfaction level. It generated r values ranging from .383 to .781, which were interpreted as low positive to high positive correlations, correlating LMX Manifestation and Job Satisfaction. The computed probability values of .000 were less than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This implies that the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) has a meaningful impact on job satisfaction. When leaders and employees share strong relationships built on trust, respect, and mutual responsibility, employees tend to feel more satisfied with their jobs. Supervisors' support and empowerment contribute to a more positive and fulfilling work experience.

Moreover, Ariani et al. (2024) highlighted that employees who receive high-quality LMX are better equipped to handle challenges at work because they feel that the company supports them. This positively impacted employee dedication to the company and happiness. Thus, to minimize the existence of in-groups and out-groups and to promote equality, the leadership must maintain good ties with every employee.

In addition, Bindra et al. (2025) suggested that managers must foster high-quality leader-member exchange (LMX) relationships with their subordinates to enhance work satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions. It indicated that implementing employee-centric policies can enhance perceived organizational support.

Lastly, Kizrak et al. (2025) found that Leader-Member Exchange had little impact on turnover intention. It was emphasized. However, job satisfaction mediated LMX's desire to leave.

Research Question 7: *Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?*

A comprehensive training plan titled Project—BIÑAN (Building Inclusive Networks to Advance Nurturing Workplaces) “Enhancing LMX, Job Satisfaction, and Performance through Inclusive Leadership and Engagement” was created to enhance job satisfaction and performance among SDO Biñan personnel by improving leader-member relationships. It empowers supervisors and staff to build stronger connections, fostering a more motivated and productive work environment.

Conclusions

1. That effective communication where expectations and feedback are openly shared, allowing both parties to understand each other's satisfaction. This

transparency fosters trust, respect, and psychological safety, contributing to a positive work environment. It also suggests a culture of openness and accountability that encourages honest dialogue and continuous growth, highlighting strong relationships and effective leadership or followership within the organization. That the level of leader-member exchange (LMX) manifestation, as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel, is anchored with a strong connection between one another. The level of trust and respect between the leader and member can determine relationship strength. Additionally, this implies that high-quality relationships thrive positively, however, low-quality relationships may result to poor leader-member exchange manifestation.

2. That the assessment of level of leader-member exchange (LMX) manifestation as assessed by Supervisors and Personnel of SDO Biñan implies mutual understanding and agreement. This viewpoint suggests that both parties view their interactions similarly, which may lead to numerous positive effects.
3. That the task performance among SDO Biñan supervisors and personnel is notably high is evident from the overall assessment score of 2.82. Most prioritize organizational development, enhancing productivity, engagement, and teamwork. However, the lowest score reflects reluctance to volunteer for extra tasks, which may strain staff and affect morale. Contextual performance varies, with a general willingness to assist colleagues, promoting collaboration and job satisfaction—though excessive support may risk burnout. Adaptive performance is also strong (score: 3.34), showing professionalism and inclusivity, though some hesitate to seek help when overwhelmed.
4. That SDO Biñan supervisors and staff believe GSIS, PAG-IBIG, and PhilHealth benefits can support family emergencies reflects confidence in government aid. Compensation and benefits were rated satisfactory (score: 2.78), with most believing they meet future needs, though some still seek educational and performance-based incentives. That most personnel show respect and positivity toward colleagues enhances the organization's image, yet mechanisms for resolving workplace conflicts remain limited. The working environment was rated satisfactory (score: 3.14), with respect highly valued, but conflict resolution needing improvement. That professional growth is important is evident, with employees receiving financial support for training and development. This area was also rated satisfactory (score: 3.08), though some are unsure about promotion pathways. That job functions matter is clear, with personnel expressing satisfaction in their roles (score: 3.08), although attention to formal job descriptions remains low.
5. That LMX manifestation is significantly related to the Job Performance Level of SDO Biñan Personnel. This implies that the higher the LMX Manifestation, the higher the Job Performance.

6. That Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) significantly associates with job satisfaction. Quality LMX relationships based on trust, respect, and obligation boost employee job satisfaction. Employees are happier at work when they feel supported and empowered by their superiors.
7. That comprehensive training program is developed to maintain and enhance the job performance and job satisfaction of SDO Biñan Personnel by addressing gaps in leader-member relationships. The initiative equips supervisors and personnel to enhance the quality of LMX and further increase the level of performance and satisfaction in the organization.

Recommendations

1. Supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan City may prioritize maintaining the high-quality leader-member exchange. Leaders must promote trust-building, encourage clear communication, avoid prejudice, offer developmental opportunities, and regularly review relationships with all team members to maintain exceptional Leader-Member Exchange (LMX). This strategy creates fair and helpful relationships between the leader and team, improving job satisfaction and performance.
2. Maintain a shared perception between supervisors and personnel. Offer diverse learning opportunities, including projects, training programs, and alternative positions, to enhance skill development among team members. Leaders must consistently exhibit integrity and fairness, treating all members with respect, especially regarding opportunities for growth. By implementing these strategies, leaders can foster a more conducive and efficient work environment where perceptions are aligned, improving team performance and member satisfaction.
3. Coaching and mentorship can enhance Employee engagement and skill development. It can be beneficial for supervisors and personnel to acknowledge the variations in LMX partnerships and modify leadership strategies appropriately. SDO Biñan Personnel needs to comprehend the social exchange component of LMX, in which employees return favorable actions.
4. Job satisfaction plays a vital role in the outcomes of an organization. Provide competitive remuneration and benefits packages that appeal to employees. Convey organizational stability and instill a sense of job security among personnel. Ensure that supervisors and personnel of SDO Biñan comprehend their jobs, responsibilities, and performance objectives. Create feedback mechanisms that can help identify issues and concerns about employees' concerns.
5. Strategies like consistent training and professional development, ongoing performance review and coaching, and establishing clear job objectives are examples of interventions that concentrate on Leader-Member Exchange and, in turn, improve job performance. SDO Biñan can improve LMX relationships and job

performance by implementing these measures and fostering a more upbeat and encouraging work atmosphere.

6. Relationships between leaders and members are strongly associated with higher levels of job satisfaction. The work environment was the primary source of satisfaction at SDO Biñan. Maintaining a more conducive working environment should be SDO Biñan's top priority. Data from regular job satisfaction surveys might help improve workplace culture and motivate employees.
7. A comprehensive action plan may be implemented to improve communication, optimize resource allocation, and promote professional development at all organizational locations. This plan must include consistent training sessions, fair resource allocation, and the establishment of effective evaluation and monitoring tools.
8. Future researchers may explore the leader-member relationship in other areas of Laguna, beyond Biñan City, and across various industries. This study can serve as a reference for leader-member exchange manifestations influencing job performance and job satisfaction. Further studies may consider demographic profile, educational attainment, or individual income using diverse methodologies and strategies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study on leader-member exchange, job performance, and job satisfaction among Biñan City's Schools' Division Office personnel strictly adhered to ethical standards. Participants were informed of the study's purpose, their voluntary role, and their right to withdraw at any time. Confidentiality and data privacy were safeguarded through informed consent and secure data handling, in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Permissions were obtained for research tools and site access, ensuring respect for intellectual property and institutional guidelines. All data was used solely for academic purposes, upholding transparency, respect, and participant welfare throughout.

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